

PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND DIDACTIC GAMES IN TEACHING ENGLISH IN A MODERN EDUCATIONAL ENVIRONMENT

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Abstract. *Taking into account how important it is to know the English language today, information about pedagogical technologies and didactic games used in the process of teaching English to students, as well as comments on the achievements based on them, are reflected in this article.*

Keywords: *english, didactic games, pedagogical technologies, information and communication technologies, innovative methods.*

Nowadays, English language is widely used in all fields of the world. Teaching and learning English is very important in the age of rapid development of information technologies and innovative technologies. For this reason, the issue of teaching English requires seriousness and deep attention every day. In the conditions of rapid development of the process of international integration and information exchange, experts in any field need a tool that allows effective exchange of professional information, in addition to traditional training. Such a tool is a professionally oriented language or a language for special purposes. It is also worth noting that officials at various levels in the country today emphasize that students must have a reliable command of the English language.

With the rapid development of computer technology and the improvement of value, the information society is experiencing drastic changes related to the acquisition of knowledge. These dramatic changes brought about by information and communication technologies have brought a new paradigm to education. Currently, as a representative of information technology, multimedia technology, network technology and satellite transmission technology are developing very rapidly. Modern educational technologies based on information technologies play an important role in the modernization of education. Modern educational technologies have a significant impact on the ideas, forms, process, teaching and management methods of education. The use of modern educational technologies in teaching English will be the driving force of innovation in the field of continuing education. The use of modern educational theory and modern information technologies makes it possible to achieve effective development of English language teaching.

Today, the interest of the young generation in learning foreign languages, especially English, is increasing. Therefore, in order to teach this language more deeply in secondary schools, pedagogues are required to use innovative methods. For example, computer technologies allow teachers to make their lessons more interactive, more interesting and useful. Based on practical experience, this method has been shown to improve students' performance. Because the lessons will be more memorable and therefore the students will be able to retain the information in their memories more effectively. Teachers and students can find memories online that can provide inspiration and tips for lessons. Teachers can also recommend good resources for their students and further encourage their learning. In addition to computer technologies, the use of new

technologies and methods is one of the approaches in today's modern education. These include digital television channels, DVD discs, digital radio and sophisticated forms of communication technology.

Another important aspect of teaching English is to monitor the student's ability to fully absorb information. Students in one group have different ideas, thinking, worldview and perception of information. Accordingly, the teacher should conduct the educational process based on the characteristics of the character of each student. For example, some students may have a natural ability to remember by sight, and another to remember by hearing. According to these characteristics, it is appropriate for the teacher to take into account the following 3 directions when learning English and conduct the lesson processes:

Visual learning — remembering information by seeing;

Auditory learning — remembering information by hearing;

Kinesthetic learning — remembering information through actions.

Taking into account the above features, the teacher will create a significant result if he explains or organizes the topics through didactic games during practical exercises, preparing role plays, and increases the student's motivation to learn the language.

Who is faster? — the purpose of the didactic game is focused on the development of students' writing technique. The course of the game is as follows: the listeners are given cards with sentences written on them, and the words of the sentences on the cards are arranged in order. The student who writes first and in the correct order will be the winner. This educational game is more effective in higher grades.

The continuing story - educational game is one of the pedagogical technologies that can be used to effectively teach English to students. Its purpose is to develop students' vocabulary. This game is based on dividing the students into two groups and giving them two types of stories in a half-finished state, and the groups continue the story based on their fantasies. will go And thus it is brought to an end. Whichever group uses more new words is the winner. This didactic game teaches students to work together. That is, it does a great service in the formation of cooperation competence in students. This game also works better in higher grades.

Noisy dictation is an educational game that can be used in English language classes. On the basis of this educational game, the goal of developing English grammar in students is achieved. The students in the class are placed facing each other and the time is set, and they must be able to understand and write the words of the student in front of them while listening to each other. This game is a bit noisy and it is the noise that allows them to understand the words even in this situation. Based on this, it is possible to increase the listening technique of students in English. It is known that in English, pronounced words are not written exactly as they are heard, for example, in the word speak, the diphthong {ea} gives the sound [i] [spi:k]. If the student can understand the words correctly as a result of hearing them, then this is a good result. This game can be used in elementary and high school English classes, of course. It can be said that age and class are not important when using this educational game.

In the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach independent thinking. Today, English language teachers, relying on the experience of pedagogues from the United States of America and England, use the following innovative methods:

"Merry riddles" teaching riddles to students. This method is important in teaching English to students, they learn unfamiliar words and find the answer to riddles by thinking;

Using the *"Quick answers"* method, it is possible to increase the effectiveness of the lesson;

"Pantomime" - this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are performed and students are tired;

"Acting characters" - this method can be used in all types of English lessons. In order to teach the profession, people in professions such as "Interpreter", "Translator", "Writer", "Poet" can participate in the class and talk with the students. In this way, students' interest in the profession is also achieved;

The *"When pictures speak"* method is very convenient and helps to develop students' oral speech in teaching English. And for this, it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic;

"Creative problem solving" — to use this method, the beginning of the story is read and the end is referred to the judgment of the students;

By using the *"A chain story"* method in English classes, a step is taken towards success in improving students' oral speech and strengthening their memories.

If we take into account that the purpose of pedagogical technologies is to make the lesson more meaningful, the above-mentioned methods also serve to increase the meaningfulness of the lesson processes organized on the basis of the English language. In addition, it is of great importance in enriching students' knowledge of the English language, in ensuring that they retain the acquired knowledge in memory, in developing their oral skills, and in developing their listening skills. In short, as a result of using innovative pedagogical methods in English lessons, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech becomes fluent, and the ability to quickly and correctly answer is formed. Such methods and games instill a passion for knowledge in students. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for the lessons. In a word, many of them turn students into subjects of the educational process.

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